
Deliverable D2.5

Project Radar Technical Roadmap

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Abstract:	The Project Radar will not be operating in the void; since it will be based on the Cyberwatching.eu Project Radar, its changes to code needs to be documented and shared with the upstream project and repository. This report will provide a description of the necessary changes, the timeline of implementation, and how changes are propagated and incorporated in the upstream repository (or not). This is the result of task T2.2.
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Terms and abbreviations

Blip	A visual placeholder for a specific EU funded project in scope for the SW Radar.
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CW	The Cyberwatching.eu project
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MTRL	Marketing and Technology Readiness Levels
Radar	Used in conjunction with CW, SWF, or TW to denote the respective radar visualisation. For example, “SWF Radar” refers to the SWForum.eu Project Radar.
SW	Software
SWF	The SWForum.eu project
SWForum.eu	European forum of the software research community
TW	ThoughtWorks, a private software and IT consultancy firm.

Executive Summary

The SWForum.eu project is a CSA aiming to support a vast array of software related projects funded by the European Commission in the H2020 programme.

This deliverable is the second document to be published by Work Package 2, reflecting the necessary steps to alter for use within the SWForum.eu the research and eventual agreement on how to adopt and improve the CW Radar for the needs of the SWForum.eu project.

With SWForum.eu now taking over as the active project developing the Project Radar software from the Cyberwatching.eu project we will discuss how the software has been made available including repository choice, software license etc. This will also include necessary documentation for the products installation within the SWForum.eu website.

This deliverable incorporates changes to the underpinning software necessary to accept the utilisation of the specific taxonomy and visualisation elements chosen to best display the project degrees of freedom within the SWForum.eu project radar. It also utilises the decisions made within the work of WP4 on changes to the Marketing and Technology Readiness Levels specific to the project including the allocation of Marketing Readiness Levels to a project outputs that are software specific and the model used to create the MTRL product itself as well as the comparative scoring method.

1 Introduction

The SWForum.eu project will continue developing, maintaining and operating the Project Radar initially developed by the Cyberwatching.eu project¹. As such the SWForum.eu Radar will become the primary implementation of the Radar, where all development will be completed. For deployment within SWForum.eu of the radar there are a number of specific technical changes that are required which will extend and adapt the radar. Details of the reasons for these changing including degrees of visual freedom and filtering taxonomy changes are details in D2.4, Project Radar Taxonomies [1]. This deliverable discusses the modifications necessary to adapt the radar technology as currently available, including how support for presentations of new metadata associated with projects is included.

Section 2 will describe the underlying technical development parameters including documentation on the underlying software framework for the real-time radar as will be deployed for the SWForum.eu project. This will include lists of specific additional features that are desirable for the SWForum.eu radar over and above those within the current default radar release. This section will also describe the development lifecycle for new features/bug releases etc of the radar and establishes the environment within which the radar must be deployed. This will include specifically the mechanism by which the data that the radar displays is automatically harvested from other components within the SWForum.eu online presence.

Within the period of completing this deliverable the software developer for the radar from UOXF moved on and as such the partner has not had the expected levels of effort or key software development knowledge available. The recruitment of a replacement is expected within the next 6 weeks.

¹ <https://www.cyberwatching.eu>

2 Technical description of the SWForum.eu Radar

The Project radar software has been custom developed through the Cyberwatching.eu project where a number of sections within are hardcoded to the taxonomy of that project. There are therefore a number of steps that will be required to deploy an instance of the radar for SWForum.eu including further development work to incorporate specific additional functionality not previously seen within the currently deployed Cyberwatching.eu instance of the radar.

The radar is implemented as a full stack application using Node.js, MongoDB, Mongoose and Express. It is fully integrated as a data source with the SWForum.eu Project Hub (D4.1, Plan for dissemination, communication & stakeholder engagement [2]) which maintains the core dataset including versioning of data that may be updated including for MTRL (D2.4, Project Radar Taxonomies [1]) etc.

Due to changes in the degrees of freedom utilised within the SWForum.eu radar when compared to the Cyberwatching.eu radar a number of changes will be required to the underlying software stack and the format of the input data including metadata etc.

2.1 Specific Changes required for transition from CW to SW Radar

Table 1: details of changes required in relationship to the CW Radar for incorporation of visual elements required by the SW Radar.

Degree of Freedom	Cyberwatching	SWForum	Software Changes
Radial segmentation	6 – radial segments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Secure Systems - Verification & assurance - Operational Risk - Identity & Privacy - Cybersecurity Governance - Human Aspects 	9 radial segments made of combinations of singular or dual association with primary and secondary classifications. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tools & Techniques + Platforms - Tools & Techniques - Tools & Techniques + Languages & Frameworks - Languages & Frameworks + Tools & Techniques - Languages & Frameworks - Languages & Frameworks + Platforms 	<i>Classification</i> for each project in import data will be made up of concatenation of primary and secondary classifications. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Change to data exporter to create input data - Change to mongo DB schema definition to support classification definitions. - Visualisation of separation into three sub segments of each major third made without line separator.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Platforms + Languages & Frameworks - Platforms - Platforms + Tools & Techniques 	
Rings	5 Rings representing Assess → Trial → Adopt → Hold → Drop	4 rings representing Assess → Trial → Adopt → Hold	Database schema and import scripts further developed to support reduction in temporal segmentation. Reduce enumeration of ring within js code from 5 to 4.
Blip shape	Not used	Blips will be shaped in two different types, triangle and circle.	Project data extended to include data of inclusion in hub. Added functionality to blib renderer to calculate if render date – inclusion date > 6 months. If yes then render circle otherwise render triangle.
Blip colour	MRL & TRL in data with calculator for combined MTRL within renderer. Multiple entries for MRL & TRL supported per project. Blip colour used to show MTRL comparison with other projects in rig and segment.	MRL & TRL in data with calculator for combined MTRL within renderer. Multiple entries for MRL & TRL supported per project. Blip colour used to show MTRL score only.	Blip renderer changed to include simple product for definition of colours from data import of MRL and TRL.
Filter	Projects tagged with elements from the JRC Cybersecurity Taxonomy [3]	Projects tagged with elements from the ACM Computing Classification System (2012) ²	Filter implementation changed to better support multi-layer taxonomy. Development of code for tagging changed to take

² <https://www.acm.org/publications/class-2012-intro>

			input from specific taxonomy. Specific development to include improvements to exclusive as well as inclusive filtering.
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2.2 Timeline for development

The radar software is available in its CW from within Github via <https://github.com/DCHW75/cw-project-radar>. This is a fork from the original development repository hosted by Michel Drescher, who is no longer with UOXF and hence the project. The next section will describe the deployment of the development instance that will be required to support the changes previously outlined.

The development of the radial allocation and hence support for primary and secondary classification of projects is the singularly most important development required without which support for other changes would not be worthwhile. Once we have completed these first set of changes these will be deployed in a development instance of radar configured as described in the following section. This environment will allow initial scoring of relevant projects and their inclusion in a radar instance to understand any gross patterns that emerge and may affect later developments aims and objectives.

Based on a start of the new developer currently being recruited in project M11 then the test instance deployment is envisaged for that month. This will be followed by coding/scoring of projects and their publishing in the radar in parallel to the development of support for all features as required including production radar deployment for the deliverable D2.6, Project Radar landscape analysis V1

2.2.1 Deployment of Development Instance

To support a testing and development environment for work on the radar a docker based image is created with all appropriate software dependencies installed and configured using the predeveloped configuration script. The instructions for creation of this instance is described below.

1. [Download and install](#) Docker (and docker compose) for your target platform.
2. [Download](#) this repository as a ZIP file, or clone it using Git: `git clone https://github.com/DCHW75/cw-project-radar.git`
3. Change directory into the project repository directory just created.
4. Run the command `docker-compose up` to assemble the docker images and start the Project Radar.
5. Open <http://localhost:8080/user/login>, log in as 'admin' using the password 'temporary'.
6. Browse to <http://localhost:8080/user/account> and change the initial admin account's password.

This will give you a blank Project Radar application in production mode.

Data in the database will be stored in a persistent volume managed by Docker rather than in a MongoDB instance as per the final version. This allows different types of testing and development including project metadata extension and annotation, visualisation rendering changes and core display changes via adding users, projects, radars, MTRL scores and classifications.

2.2.2 Required environment for the production radar deployment

The production project radar sits within the whole project website (<https://www.swforum.eu>) ecosystem as deployed by Trust-IT. This is a replication of the configuration that has been successfully used for the Cyberwatching.eu project. The platform is a simple private cloud system running standard Linux virtual machines supporting the radar development stack.

3 Conclusions

Within this deliverable the outline plan for the technical changes required to deploy a SWForum.eu specific instance have been discussed. They will be detailed further in a later milestone that will include full timings of the development steps and details of any dependencies in the launching of the SWForum.eu project radar. The development of this timeline to release is though contingent on the recruitment of an appropriate developer who will be responsible for the development process of the radar within SWForum.eu.

4 References

- [1] SwForum consortium, “D2.4- Project Radar Taxonomies” 2021.
- [2] SwForum consortium, “D4.1-Plan for dissemination, communication & stakeholder engagement” 2021.
- [3] I. N. R. H. R. J. P. N. R. G. F. M. a. L. A. Nai Fovino, “A Proposal for a European Cybersecurity Taxonomy,” Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2019.